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INNOVATION PROCESS

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D2.1 Innovation process

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1. Innovation Process

The successful implementation of new ideas into technically and commercially viable products and services is a critical part of all modern economies. Unsurprisingly, it is a topic that generates continual discussion and debate although there is a broad consensus of distinct stages in any innovation process and what constitutes best practice for a particular business case. However, SUNRISE recognizes that for the transition to a circular economy we are dealing with something beyond the conventional commercial context. The problem to be solved is global in magnitude, albeit with a European epicenter. Consequently, we will need from the outset to build collaborative forums for all partners and stakeholders to meet and set priorities for addressing short, medium and long-term challenges for transitioning to a circular economy.

The most important aspect, dealing with disruptive technologies and the SUNRISE vision, is to bring fundamental research to the market through the fastest possible route. In Deliverable 1.1, the outline for the production of Hydrogen, Ammonia and Carbon-based feedstock is given in view of different possible technologies. As innovation is the sum of invention/fundamental research plus commercialization, SUNRISE will also put emphasis on the latter to push innovation forward. It is necessary to create an environment, where new start-ups are founded and funded in addition to the present industrial companies and SMEs to cover the TRL levels from TRL 4/5 to 7/8. For this, the investment climate for renewable energy solutions needs to be considered (Egli, Steffen et al. 2018). These TRLs often suffer from an absence of industrial partners, especially in the case of new disruptive technologies. Additionally, innovation cycles in the field of chemical feedstocks are quite large in the range of >10 years, as often high investments have to be made to introduce new processes or plants. Existing companies are often very risk-averse.

To encourage SUNRISE technologies to flourish, the concept of a multitude of SUNRISE Valleys is introduced in the style of the Silicon Valley (see Figure 1).

Technical areas with defined expertise are needed to introduce a kind of quality assurance for emerging SUNRISE technologies. It is necessary to implement an environment, which allows people to focus on the technology development. These areas should act as Centers of excellence, either centered geographically or virtually. These SUNRISE valleys will provide a highly agile environment: Universities, research centers, industrial players, start-ups, etc., dedicated to develop and commercialize concepts and technologies in support of the transition to a circular economy. With strong involvement of industry and particularly start-ups and SMEs, ensuring a highly agile and entrepreneurial environment in which new and also potentially risky and disruptive technologies are quickly brought from the level of an idea or technology concept to commercial application, based on a robust and realistic business model.

The SUNRISE Valleys constitute a Trans-European Network (TEN) and will fit in Europe's TEN policy (Marshall 2014). A comparable and readily existing initiative is the Hydrogen Europe network, which is spread across Europe. To further realize this concept of SUNRISE valleys and to reduce the innovation cycle time demand, the combination of public funding as well as private investments and a long-term commitment (minimum 10 years period) from the EC and the member states will be crucial. In this way, private investments can be engaged and a solid start-up financing of risky enterprises ensured.

A harmonized and comparable infrastructure of SUNRISE valleys providing support with *e.g.*, business angels, venture capital companies, Intellectual Property (IP) support, business attorneys, marketing experts, accountants, etc. will enable a fast and focused development of technologies in a business-friendly environment. In cooperation with large industry, these technologies can be distributed on a global scale to ensure the acceleration in technology distribution (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Network of SUNRISE valleys in Europe, having already interested SUNRISE supporters available.

Figure 2: Acceleration in technology development and reduction of innovation cycle is indicated with red arrows.

Additionally, SUNRISE will do this by adopting best practices from other suitable sectors/economic regions for structuring the innovation process and for handling attendant information flow including intellectual property. In other words, SUNRISE will leverage the existing Member State ‘innovation infrastructure’ to provide local nodes for assisting the overall SUNRISE Innovation Process (SIP). The SIP will be built up using well-recognized stages (outlined below). From the outset, it will be vital to create an innovation environment where contributors are purposefully exposed to the views and opinions of all stakeholders so that new concepts and approaches to converting sunlight into fuels and chemicals are in sync with the drivers that are shaping our societies of the future.

SUNRISE will bring together an innovation team as part of, and reporting to, the governance structure. The innovation team will be specifically in charge of and responsible for organizing and running the SIP. The team is expected to evolve with time to reflect new developments in the political and social European landscape as they happen. The team will be tasked with leveraging relevant resource, assistance and advice from local, national and European organizations and institutions in building the SUNRISE innovation nodes. The frequency of webinars and physical meeting-forums will be adjusted in response to specific decision points embedded in the Roadmap.

2. Stages of the Innovation Process

SUNRISE uses three principal approaches to develop solutions to the chemical and fuel-based needs of Europe’s circular economy i.e. electrochemical, photoelectrochemical and biological/biohybrid processes. As well as having different product outcomes covering hydrogen, liquid hydrocarbons and ammonia, these approaches occupy different segments of the TRL range. Nonetheless, it is anticipated that the three approaches will share inter-related technical and commercialization challenges. We consider here five distinct stages of innovation that are generally applicable across the S&T landscape. The innovation process will be operated with sufficient flexibility to account for the different SUNRISE technology themes. For example, stages 4 and 5 will have more immediate relevance to the electrochemical production of hydrogen as this has already reached demonstrator stage, but lessons learnt here will have real value for passing onto the photoelectrochemical and biological/biohybrid operations. In the following, the individual stages of the SUNRISE Innovation process are outlined. The transition of technologies from basic research to commercial application, particularly the innovation and exploitation plan (Science-to-Science and especially Science-to-Business exploitation) as part of the Innovation Process are described in more detail in the following report D2.2 and D2.3

Stage 1: Idea generation and refinement.

We need new ideas that cover all aspects of the circular economy from science and technology to funding and financing, legislation, social acceptance, and local societal needs. Especially for societal needs, a series of webinars and ‘town-hall’ meetings, where stakeholders from industry, academia, policy and private persons gather, will pick up problems to solve in a bottom-up structure. These meetings will be put in place to give full exposure of new ideas and technologies to the concept of the circular economy. Suggested technology approaches will be discussed, refined, extended, combined etc. (also criticized), thus supporting the development of ideas and concepts for the next stage of the Innovation process (Evaluation and selection). An initial list of relevant topics/thematic fields for new ideas and technology concepts is presented in Section 3.

Partnership and networking opportunities will be a feature of the physical forums to encourage cross-disciplinary interactions at an early stage. Even technologies at relatively high TRLs can benefit from new thinking and continuous refinement. A successful Stage 1 should therefore provide potential participants with a well-rounded view of the problem to be solved and what their technical projects should encompass to be relevant progressing the Roadmap.

Stage 2: Evaluation and selection

The governance structure of SUNRISE allows for the selection of projects, as proposed from Stage 1, for consideration for funding by the commission and other sources of finance from private and/or public bodies. In keeping with most R&D initiatives, ‘call’ gateways at this stage would typically include (i) Being within scope of a particular call, (ii) Having a well-defined technical challenge, (iii) Clarity of desired output, market potential and potential impact, (iv) A risk management strategy, (v) An appropriate team with well-matched resources and tasks, (vi) A logical cost basis and budget management plan and (vii) Clear quantifiable objectives and targets.

To build and retain credibility, the evaluation process must be transparent and standardized, as not every idea will survive close scrutiny and feedback should be constructive. The choice of reviewers for proposals must reflect the circular economy’s stakeholders in addition to technical excellence.

Stage 3: Experimentation

The three SUNRISE technology approaches will be starting from different TRLs, and have specific targets that reflect a combination of ambition and realism in reaching for higher TRLs highlighted in the Roadmap. Likely, some projects will run into difficulties and some will achieve at least part of their principal objectives. In either case, provision must be made for interim, decision and end review points. Partners will be strongly encouraged to take *calculated* risks and to look for common-sense short-cuts to move science and technology as quickly as possible towards practical demonstration. The SIP team will provide continual support by providing a contact point at local nodes for advice and guidance covering technical and administrative issues including how to deal with arising IP issues and conflicts, partner changes and accessing national and European S&T infrastructure such as advanced physical characterization methods.

Stage 4: Commercialization

In the approach to the commercialization stage, the SUNRISE partners should continuously consult end-users to verify that the innovation actually solves problems that are relevant to industry and society as a whole. Partners will need to carefully analyze the costs and benefits of rolling out the innovation. As the TRL increases, new people and partnerships may need to be involved. This can necessitate the decoupling from academic input and moving towards commercialization through business operations that cover the spectrum from spin-offs to large multinationals. Many factors come into play depending on the nature of the business endeavor such as spin-off vs large industrial company, member state and EU-level financial incentives, subsidies or taxation, fossil-fuel prices, potential carbon taxes, and possible rapid market shifts such as change in plastics usage.

Stage 5: Implementation

Implementation is typically the most challenging stage as the required investment levels rapidly increase, as do the associated risks of not achieving anticipated sales revenues. The full commercialization of processes aiming at the production of fuels and chemicals from solar/CO₂/N₂/H₂O will take time and the SUNRISE partners view the roll-out pathways as evolutionary with early targets focused on local customer bases where conditions are the most conducive to mitigate costs and maximize benefits. In this respect, SUNRISE expects to build on the lessons learnt from the rapid growth of renewable energy generation (wind, solar etc.) and electrification of automotive drive-trains. Importantly, there will be a strong emphasis on using the nodes to seek and exploit early revenue opportunities to build credibility with stakeholders.

3. The SIP action plan

Creation of the SIP Team

SIP Team members will be drawn from SUNRISE members/stakeholders and in particular from WP2 contributors. The SIP Team will be responsible for the creation of a “template” SUNRISE valley, which can be

adopted throughout Europe. Therefore, the SIP Team will be responsible to manage the search of local partners with expertise in *e.g.*, bookkeeping, business angels, VC companies, IP support, lawyers, marketing experts etc. for each valley. The SIP Team will manage especially stage 1 of the innovation process and will actively support interested consortia to bridge from stage 1 to stage 2 until stage 5.

Design of webinar and forum contents

Topics will include expert speakers on

- (i) The circular economy
- (ii) Cities of the future
- (iii) The future of Plastics
- (iv) Hydrogen infrastructure
- (v) The carbon credit/tax landscape
- (vi) Agriculture for the future

and other topics with a timetable that dovetails with the Roadmap requirements.

Selection of national SUNRISE nodes

The SUNRISE Innovation Process team will use local knowledge from the representative Member State SUNRISE supporters to quickly establish national SUNRISE nodes. We emphasize that the opportunities for Europe to capitalize on the circular economy depend both on our will and ability to innovate and on how rapid we can translate innovative technological solutions into large-scale industrial processes.

Information flow and intellectual property matters

To encourage free-thinking and exchange of ideas amongst the SUNRISE community and stakeholders, rules of engagement for each event will be made clear. Protection of IP in partnerships will be based on the European Commission's DESCA¹ template. Attention will be paid to on-line dissemination as well as traditional publication routes and so participants will be encouraged to use the SUNRISE website where appropriate.

References

Egli, F., B. Steffen and T. S. Schmidt (2018). "A dynamic analysis of financing conditions for renewable energy technologies." *Nature Energy* **3**(12): 1084-1092.

Marshall, T. (2014). "The European Union and Major Infrastructure Policies: The Reforms of the Trans-European Networks Programmes and the Implications for Spatial Planning." *European Planning Studies* **22**(7): 1484-1506.

¹ Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement, <http://www.desca-agreement.eu/about-desca/what-is-desca/>

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